

SpectraStream tutorial

<https://spectra.adma.ai/stream>

Introduction

The SpectraStream application for harmonizing Raman spectroscopy data is a user interface to perform wavenumber calibration and relative intensity calibration according to the [CWA 18133:2024](#) developed by CHARISMA project. SpectraStream uses the open source **ramanchada2** <https://github.com/h2020charisma/ramanchada2> Python library, implementing Raman spectra pre-processing, peak finding and fitting, and calibration. The x-axis calibration requires the measurement of a neon emission spectrum and a silicon Raman spectrum as references, whereas the spectrum of a NIST standard reference material (SRM) or a calibrated broad-band emission lamp are the references for the y-axis.

Step 1: Load Instrument Settings

The first step in harmonizing Raman spectra is ensuring that the application is aware of the key instrument-specific parameters. On the **"Load Instrument Settings"** page (Fig. 1), users are prompted to input essential details about their spectroscopy setup, such as:

- **Laser wavelength, in nm:** This is critical for ensuring correct alignment between the Raman signal and the calibration process.
- **Instrument make and model.**
- **Other instrument-specific information:** These include details reflecting the optical path. The uploaded spectra files should be from **the same optical path..**

Load instrument metadata

Make And Model Of The Instrument

Serial Number Of The Instrument

Lazer wavelength (nm) Units: nm

 - +

Device Type

Numerical Aperture

Grating

Slit

Fig. 1 Load instrument settings

Once the instrument settings are defined, users proceed to the "**Load or Create Calibration**" , described below. "**Create calibration**" option has two steps, "**Create x-calibration**" and "**Create y-calibration**" .

Step 2: Create X-axis or wavenumber calibration.

Once the instrument settings are defined, users proceed to the "**Load or Create Calibration**" page, where they will conduct **X-calibration** using a Ne spectrum and a Si spectrum, obtained **using the same optical path and spectral range**. The following steps are essential for preparing the neon calibration data. Please ensure that all uploaded spectra are **dark subtracted**.

1. **Load Neon Raw Spectrum:** A Ne spectrum is needed to derive a wavenumber calibration curve by matching the fitted peak positions with the reference values from NIST.
2. **Neon Preprocessing Operations:** The neon spectrum may be subjected to a series of preprocessing steps, all accessible through dedicated tabs, as shown in **Figure 2**:
 - a. **Crop:** The spectrum is cropped to focus on a specific range along the X-axis. This is useful for removing irrelevant parts of the spectrum (optional).
 - b. **Normalize:** The intensity values on the Y-axis are min-max normalized (optional).
 - c. **Peak Find:** Peaks in the neon spectrum are identified. These are used to build a model and also serve as initial guesses for peak fitting..
 - d. **Peak Fit:** The peaks are fitted using appropriate models to obtain precise peak positions that will be matched to the reference NIST)
 - e. **Derive X-Calibration curve:** Ne peaks are used to derive the calibration curve. Skipping the peak fitting step is possible, however using peak estimates based only on the previous step will decrease the accuracy of the calibration.

Charisma Home Page

- Load instrument settings
- Load or create calibration**
- Apply calibration

Instrument settings -----

laser_wavelength: 532

Choose calibration option

Load Calibration

Create Calibration

Create X-Calibration

Neon spectrum

Derive X-Calibration curve

Si spectrum

Lazer zeroing

Calibration file name

calibration_file_name.pkl

Download X-Calibration

Fig 2. Ne spectrum preprocessing steps.

Fig 3. Ne spectrum peak finding and fitting, matching to the reference Ne peaks

For the Si spectrum we have the same steps of preprocessing as Ne, with an additional tab for Baseline subtraction. The preprocessing options are given on Fig 4. It is recommended to crop the spectrum around the Silicon peak.

Fig 4. Silicon spectrum suggested preprocessing steps: Cropping around the silicon peak and baseline subtraction.

Update

window length: 200 - +
 prominence: 5.00 - +
 width: 2 - +
 strategy: topo ▾

Download Peaks found (CSV)

Fig 4. Silicon peak finding

When the preprocessing step of Silicon spectrum is accomplished after applying the “**Laser zeroing**” the user should see a plot similar to the one of Fig 5. The laser zeroing is explained in [CWA:1833](#) Section2. The silicon peak is then used to find the laser zero position and convert the wavelength x-axis to the Raman-shift x-axis.

There is the option to download the X-calibration model to be able to reuse it in the future.

Fig 5. The x-calibration plots, illustrating Ne spectrum peak found and matched to the references , as well as the result of applying the x-calibration to the Si spectrum.

To ensure robust workflow for creating x-calibration, we recommend pre-processing, namely, load the spectra from file, crop Ne if necessary, and crop the Si spectra around the expected peak. Normalization (minmax) is also recommended in order to use the default peak finding options (e.g., prominence), otherwise they should be adapted.

Step 3: Create Y-axis or Relative Intensity Calibration

The relative intensity correction shall be performed after the calibration of x-axis, as the conversion formula requires the use of the x-axis values.

y-axis correction involves the measurement of a certified reference material that can be:

- NIST SRM fluorescent glass sample
- Traceable LED light source (e.g. ELODIZ Raman intensity correction LEDs)
- Traceable incandescent lamp (e.g. Tungsten)

The expected curve will accompany the sample, usually in the form of a formula, and shall be compared to the measured curve. The ratio between the two is used to apply a multiplier to each pixel's intensity value.

Once the x axis is calibrated, users proceed to the "**Load or Create Calibration**" page, where they will conduct **Y-calibration**. The following steps are essential for preparing the calibration data:

1. Dark Subtraction

Before proceeding with Y-calibration, please check that the uploaded spectrum is **dark subtracted**

2. Creating the Relative Intensity Calibration

Once the dark subtraction is performed, the Y-calibration process begins. The calibration requires the use of **SRM certificates**, which are implemented in the **YCalibrationCertificate** class of the Ramanchada2 (rc2) library. A collection of **NIST SRM** (Standard Reference Material) and **LED (Elodiz)** certificates is available and can be accessed using the **CertificateDict** class.

The Y-calibration widget expects **two inputs**:

- The **spectrum to be calibrated**.
- The **measured spectrum of reference**, such as a NIST SRM.

The user must also select the appropriate **SRM certificate** from the options in the widget's sidebar. The certificates ensure that the calibration aligns with industry standards, making the spectra consistent across different instruments.

Y-Calibration Process

The following steps (and corresponding buttons in the SpectraStream app's sidebar) guide users through the Y-calibration (Fig 6.):

- **Choose Reference Material Certificate:** Select the SRM or LED certificate that corresponds to the reference material used for calibration (Fig 7.)
- **SRM Experimental:** Allows for further adjustments and experimental analysis using the SRM data (Fig 8)
- **Derive Y-Calibration:** This step applies the Y-calibration using the selected certificate and the provided spectra, adjusting the intensity values for standardization.

Choose calibration option

Load Calibration

Create Calibration

Create X-Calibration

Create Y-Calibration

WaveLength: 532

Certificate reference material

NIST532_SRM2242a

SRM Experimental

Derive Y-calibration

Calibration file name

ycalibration_file_name.pkl

Download Y-Calibration

Fig 6. Sidebar for the Y-Calibration options

On the next Fig 7., there is an example of Certificate reference material, as defined in https://github.com/h2020charisma/ramanchada2/blob/main/src/ramanchada2/protocols/config_certs.json

Fig 7. Example of Certificate reference material.

Fig 8. SRM experimental with the pre-processing options of Crop and Smooth.

After pushing the Derive Y-Calibration button, the Y-Calibration model is saved (Fig 8.) and can be Downloaded from the side bar (Fig.6).

Fig 8. Y-Calibration model is saved

Step 4: Apply Calibration (X and/or Y-Calibration)

After the X-Calibration and/or Y-Calibration model have been created or loaded from existing pickled files they can be used in the section Apply Calibration. We have the two options: X and Y-Calibration as shown on Fig 9. The user should choose a target spectrum to be calibrated, which is represented in the first button on the sidebar for the calibration and similar to Fig 2. and Fig 4. the user is able to apply some preprocessing on the target spectrum, such as Crop, Normalize, etc.

Fig 9. Sidebar for the execution of the Calibration: X and/or Y-calibration.

The following widget (on Fig. 10) encapsulates the following operations: 1) Neon spectrum peak finding and fitting, matching to the reference Ne peaks and deriving the calibration curve; 2) Laser zeroing using Si peak 3) applying the calibration curve and the laser zeroing formula to the test spectra. The third step is for verification only, it does not affect the calibration model. The matched Ne peaks are shown on the top chart. The effect of laser zeroing is shown at the middle chart. The bottom chart shows the original and calibrated test spectra (could be one or more). Once ready, the X-calibrated spectrum can be downloaded.

[Download X-Calibrated spectrum \(CSV\)](#)

Fig 10. Example of target spectrum X-calibration plot with the option to download the calibrated spectrum

[Download Y-Calibrated spectrum \(CSV\)](#)

Fig 11. Example of target spectrum Y-calibration plot with the option to download the Y-calibrated spectrum

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